

Solvent Effect on the Aquation of Octahedral Cobalt(III) Complexes

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Manuscript received 20 March 1987, revised 12 January 1988, accepted 17 March 1988

The aquation of $trans-[Co(3-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ and $trans-[Co(4-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ cations (Etpy=ethylpyridine) was studied in a wide range of water+acetonitrile and water+dioxane mixtures at different temperatures. A non-linear relation obtained for the variation of \log (rate constant) with the reciprocal of the dielectric constant, for both the complexes in the two aqueous mixed solvents, indicates that the effect of solvent structure is of great importance. The activation thermodynamic parameters were calculated. The application of a free energy cycle showed that changes in solvent structure affect the complex cations in the transition state more than the initial state. The nature of the complex ligands play an important role in the solvation of the cation. However, it depends to a great extent upon the properties of the solvent.

SPONTANEOUS aquation of several cobalt(III) complexes¹⁻⁴ has been investigated in different aqueous alcohols in connection with the elucidation of the interaction nature of the solvent with the complex, and the magnitude of this interaction in both the ground and transition states. This work presents the aquation of $trans-[Co(3-Etpy)_4Cl_2]ClO_4$ and $trans-[Co(4-Etpy)_4Cl_2]ClO_4$ in aqueous acetonitrile and aqueous dioxane in order to assess the role of the nature of the ligands and the solvation of the reacting complex ions.

Experimental

The chlorides of the complex cations, $trans-[Co(3-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ and $trans-[Co(4-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ were prepared by a procedure analogous to that used⁵ for $trans-[Co(py)_4Cl_2]Cl$. The perchlorates of the complex cations were prepared as described earlier⁶. Acetonitrile⁷ and dioxane⁸ (B.D.H.) were further purified.

Preliminary experiments: The spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 8-400 spectrophotometer were studied in water at 25°. Both the complexes showed a maximum at the same wavelength (233 nm) with $\epsilon = 2.30 \times 10^4$ and $4.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $trans-[Co(3-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ and $trans-[Co(4-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ respectively. No maximum was observed in the visible region of the spectra owing to the low solubility of the salts in water and in aquo-organic mixtures, where the concentration of the measured solutions was $1.52 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$. During the aquation a decay in the optical density was observed at 233 nm and no isosbestic points were detected. The addition of the organic solvent to water did not change the spectra of the complexes.

Kinetic procedure: The aquation rate was measured spectrophotometrically using a Perkin-

Elmer 550A spectrophotometer. The complex was dissolved in water or in aqueous organic solvent at the temperature being investigated. The initial concentration was $1.52 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ for both $trans-[Co(3-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$ and $trans-[Co(4-Etpy)_4Cl_2]^+$. The decay of the optical density with time was measured at 233 nm in the thermostated cell compartment of the spectrophotometer. The temperatures were controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The reaction mixture was left overnight at the experiment temperature to measure the infinity value corresponding to the complete aquation of the complex.

Results and Discussion

Aquation of $trans-[Co(3-Etpy)_4Cl_2]ClO_4$ and $trans-[Co(4-Etpy)_4Cl_2]ClO_4$ were investigated in water and in water+co-solvent ranging from 0.0 to 70% (v/v) acetonitrile or dioxane. The aquation rates for each mixture were studied in the temperature range 40–55°. First order kinetics were observed up to 70% of complete reaction. The rate constants were calculated from the averages of duplicate or triplet determinations. The values are compiled in Table 1.

Variation of rate constant with temperature: The plot of $\log k$ vs T^{-1} at constant solvent composition is linear. Activation energies and the activation thermodynamic parameters, ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger were calculated for each mixture using all the individual values of the rate constant by applying the least-squares procedure. These values and their standard deviations are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The non-linear change of both the activation energy (ΔE^\ddagger) and the activation entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) with the mole fraction of the co-solvent (X_2) may be ascribed to the differential solvation of the complex cations in the initial and transition states. Consequently, non-random distribution is expected for the solvent molecules around such species.

Variation of rate constant with solvent composition: The aquation reaction of the octahedral complexes of the type $[\text{CoL}_4\text{X}_2]^+$, takes place by S_N^1 (I_d) mechanism⁹ according to the equations,

TABLE 1 FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT ($k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$)^a FOR AQUATION OF COMPLEX CATIONS IN SOLVENT MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Solvent wt%	$[\text{Co}(4\text{-Etpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$					$[\text{Co}(3\text{-Etpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$				
	40°	45°	50°	55°	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	40°	45°	50°	55°	ΔE^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
Water + Dioxan mixture										
0.00	4.17	9.06	13.11	21.62	90.79 ±5.65	8.30	14.30	27.98	46.83	104.79 ±2.10
10.20	6.92	13.02	20.62	34.33	91.24 ±1.61	8.71	17.54	37.42	67.65	117.62 ±2.39
20.46	4.89	10.14	19.35	30.63	104.59 ±3.65	7.31	17.10	32.28	56.62	115.97 ±4.17
30.60	4.14	6.98	13.99	31.45	115.69 ±5.35	9.08	15.34	29.77	57.36	106.43 ±2.91
40.68	3.79	6.57	13.81	24.31	107.81 ±3.03	6.91	13.22	24.73	42.44	103.79 ±1.90
50.71	3.80	7.15	12.74	23.65	103.95 ±1.92	9.37	16.37	26.83	44.18	96.77 ±1.28
60.68	4.27	7.76	13.41	23.29	97.45 ±2.50	6.64	15.12	24.63	53.37	119.21 ±4.59
70.50	4.22	6.59	14.59	22.87	100.16 ±5.25	8.10	16.95	26.51	54.50	105.49 ±4.32
Water + ACN mixture										
0.00	4.17	9.06	13.11	21.62	90.79 ±5.65	8.30	14.30	27.98	46.83	104.79 ±2.10
7.99	4.37	6.97	13.14	20.43	89.99 ±2.88	8.46	14.41	33.91	55.18	106.60 ±5.78
16.35	4.04	7.61	12.76	21.69	95.16 ±1.81	11.05	18.27	37.56	65.06	102.83 ±3.71
25.10	3.93	7.49	12.77	21.94	93.74 ±4.29	11.06	19.36	38.02	65.25	102.98 ±2.35
34.20	4.41	7.01	16.31	28.67	109.14 ±4.57	14.17	26.42	38.77	62.70	82.81 ±3.35
43.89	4.70	8.76	16.31	27.14	100.52 ±1.73	11.64	25.16	48.46	64.00	97.88 ±7.77
55.98	4.68	7.96	16.38	26.15	106.27 ±5.28	15.82	32.15	49.42	83.16	92.54 ±3.81
64.60	4.94	8.54	18.94	26.70	100.35 ±6.65	16.80	31.80	52.89	74.85	85.15 ±4.72

^a Average values.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC DATA FOR COMPLEX CATIONS IN SOLVENT MIXTURES

Solvent wt%	$[\text{Co}(4\text{-Etpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$			$[\text{Co}(3\text{-Etpy})_2\text{Cl}_2]^+$		
	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Water + Dioxane mixture						
0.00	88.31 ±5.65	102.15 ±10.90	46.43 ±17.62	102.31 ±2.10	101.53 ±4.06	-2.61 ±6.56
10.20	88.78 ±1.61	101.13 ±3.12	41.48 ±5.01	115.14 ±2.39	101.83 ±4.61	-44.65 ±7.46
20.46	102.12 ±3.65	102.52 ±7.03	1.34 ±11.35	113.49 ±4.17	102.02 ±8.05	-38.47 ±13.00
30.60	113.21 ±5.35	103.79 ±10.32	-31.60 ±16.69	103.95 ±2.91	101.30 ±5.69	-8.89 ±9.07
40.68	105.33 ±3.03	103.50 ±5.84	-6.14 ±9.44	101.31 ±1.90	101.70 ±3.67	1.31 ±5.94
50.71	101.47 ±1.92	103.24 ±3.70	5.91 ±5.98	94.29 ±1.28	100.13 ±2.46	-25.14 ±3.98
60.68	94.97 ±2.50	102.60 ±4.83	25.29 ±7.81	116.73 ±4.59	102.52 ±8.55	-47.66 ±14.31
70.50	97.68 ±5.28	102.90 ±10.18	17.50 ±16.46	103.01 ±4.34	101.37 ±3.38	-5.51 ±13.54

(Table 2 contd.)

Water + ACN mixture						
0.00	88.31	102.15	46.43	102.81	101.58	-2.61
	± 5.65	± 10.90	± 17.62	± 2.10	± 4.06	± 5.65
7.99	87.62	102.27	49.47	104.13	101.81	-9.43
	± 2.88	± 5.57	± 8.99	± 5.78	± 11.61	± 18.03
16.95	92.62	102.60	33.46	100.35	100.63	0.94
	± 1.81	± 3.49	± 5.65	± 3.71	± 7.17	± 11.59
25.10	91.26	102.51	37.72	104.50	100.58	0.27
	± 4.29	± 8.27	± 13.87	± 2.35	± 4.54	± 7.34
34.20	106.66	103.23	-11.50	80.33	98.84	62.08
	± 4.57	± 8.83	± 14.26	± 3.35	± 6.48	± 10.47
48.89	98.04	102.50	14.97	95.40	99.91	15.11
	± 1.73	± 3.35	± 5.41	± 7.77	± 15.01	± 24.26
55.98	103.39	102.92	2.91	90.06	99.01	30.01
	± 5.28	± 10.16	± 16.39	± 3.81	± 7.36	± 11.90
64.60	97.87	102.37	15.09	82.67	98.47	53.00
	± 6.65	± 12.84	± 20.74	± 4.72	± 9.11	± 14.72

TABLE 3—VALUES OF LEFT-HAND SIDE OF EQUATION (5) (kJ mol⁻¹) IN AQUEOUS SOLVENT MIXTURES

Complex cation	Dioxan (wt%)				
	10.20	20.46	30.60	40.68	50.71
<i>trans</i> -[Co(4-Mepy) ₄ Cl ₂] ⁺	-1.65	-4.02	-4.90	-6.87	-8.51
<i>trans</i> -[Co(4-Etpty) ₄ Cl ₂] ⁺	-3.61	-6.06	-8.61	-10.84	-12.51
<i>trans</i> -[Co(3-Etpty) ₄ Cl ₂] ⁺	-2.80	-5.63	-9.13	-10.91	-14.10
	ACN (wt%)				
	7.99	16.95	25.10	34.20	48.89
<i>trans</i> -[Co(4-Mepy) ₄ Cl ₂] ⁺	-0.117	-1.40	-3.04	-3.98	-5.89
<i>trans</i> -[Co(4-Etpty) ₄ Cl ₂] ⁺	-1.91	-2.71	-4.35	-4.93	-7.05
<i>trans</i> -[Co(3-Etpty) ₄ Cl ₂] ⁺	-1.63	-4.05	-5.65	-8.69	-10.23

The change in the dielectric constant may have a considerable influence on the dissociation of the first step.

The failure of the simple electrostatic interpretation¹⁰ of the present experimental data, based on the dependence of the rate constant on the dielectric constant of the medium, led to the conclusion that the non-electrostatic part of the solvent effect overcomes the electrostatic component. Therefore, there is no continuity in the dielectric constant of the medium as proposed by the electrostatic theories. This feature concerning the environment surrounding the reacting species may be supported by the obtained activation parameters. In such cases, the differential solvation of the initial and transition states is the controlling factor for changes in the rate constant with the solvent composition.

The modified¹¹ relation of the Laidler - Landskroener equation¹²,

$$2.303 RT \log \frac{k_w}{k_s} = \frac{Ne^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{D_s} - \frac{1}{D_w} \right) \left\{ \frac{Z_M^2}{r_M} + \frac{Z_{Cl}^2}{r_{Cl}} - \frac{Z_C^2}{r_C} + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{G_M}{r_M} + \frac{G_{Cl}}{r_{Cl}} - \frac{G_C}{r_C} \right) \right\} + \Delta G_i^0(M)_n + \Delta G_i^0(Cl^-)_n - \Delta G_i^0(C)_n \quad (3)$$

where, $\Delta G_i^0(i)_n$ is the free energy of transfer of species (i) from water into the mixture excluding the contribution from the Born and Kirkwood electrostatic effects allowed for in the first term on

the right hand side of equation (3). In case of a differential effect of the solvent structure on the initial and transition states, equation (4) will hold,

$$\Delta G_i^0(C^{ZC})_n \neq \Delta G_i^0(M^{ZM})_n + \Delta G_i^0(Cl^-)_n \quad (4)$$

where, C^{ZC} and M^{ZM} represent the complex cation in the ground and transition states, respectively.

The comparison¹³ of the volume of activation ΔV^\ddagger with the overall volume change ΔV^0 for the aquation of complexes of the type $[Co(L)_4Cl_2]^+$ and by other stereochemical methods¹⁴, it was concluded that the $Co^{+3} \dots Cl^-$ bond is extremely extended in the transition state nearly to 100% ionisation. This suggests that the aquation of such complexes proceeds via an I_a mechanism. This fact permits the application of the following equation to the complexes under investigation,

$$2.303 RT \log \frac{k_w}{k_s} - \Delta G_i^0(Cl^-) = \Delta G_i^0(M^{Z+1}) - \Delta G_i^0(M^Z) \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) was deduced from a free energy cycle constructed by Wells¹¹ relating ΔG^\ddagger with $\Delta G_i^0(i)$ for the S_N2 type solvolysis of a metal complex MX^Z with extremely extending $M \dots X$ bond in the transition state.

Values of k_w and k_s at 25° were calculated from the activation thermodynamic parameters given in Table 2, those values together with $\Delta G_i^0(Cl^-)$ found

in the literature^{15,16} allowed us to calculate the left-hand side of equation (5). The results are presented in Table 3 and graphically in Fig. 1, the complex cation¹⁷ $trans-[Co(4-Mepy)_4Cl_2]^+$ data have been included for comparison. The salient

Fig. 1. Variation of left-hand side (L.H.S.) of eqn. (5) with mole fraction in (A) H_2O+ACN and (B) $H_2O+dioxan$ mixtures: (●) $[Co(4-Mepy)_4Cl_2]^+$, (○) $[Co(4-Etpty)_4Cl_2]^+$ and (◐) $[Co(3-Etpty)_4Cl_2]^+$.

feature of the data of Table 3, is the negative values of the left-hand side of equation (5) which thus indicates that the effect of changing solvent structure is greater on the pentacoordinated cation in the transition state than on the hexacoordinated cation in the initial state¹¹. This type of complexes showed similar behaviour in other water+co-solvents¹⁻⁴, and this is quite in agreement with the electrostatic grounds where the charge on the activated cation is double that on the cation in the initial state.

The inductive effect of the ligand heteroatom¹⁸ along the C-N σ -bond rises the electron affinity of

the α -carbon atom, and the change in charge density depends on the environment of the atom. From Fig. 1, one may conclude that this polarisability is more significant for $trans-[Co(3-Etpty)_4Cl_2]^+$ cation particularly in water+acetonitrile mixtures. Acetonitrile is known as a strongly differentiating solvent¹⁹, and when mixed with water the system becomes highly basic relative to water+dioxane. The high basicity of the former system may be attributed to the formation of intercomponent hydrogen-bonded complexes²⁰ resulting in an increased basicity of the hydroxyl oxygen atom which enhances the interaction with the complex cation of higher charge density.

The similar differential effect of water+dioxane mixtures towards the investigated complex cations indicates that the levelling effect in this connection may be ascribed to the symmetry in dioxane molecule which makes this solvent less polar among other solvents, and it induces no considerable influence on the basicity of water. Moreover, dioxane is known to have a dehydration effect²¹, since ions like Bu_4N^+ loses its structure-making properties continuously as dioxane is added to water.

In conclusion, the nature of the ligand and the differential effect of the solvent mixture on the initial and transition states, which in turn depends on the solvent structure, are of great importance.

References

1. I. M. SIDAHMED and C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 1035.
2. I. M. SIDAHMED and A. M. ISMAIL, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1986, 11, 288.
3. I. M. SIDAHMED and C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1969.
4. C. N. ELGY and C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 2405.
5. A. WERNER and R. FERNSTRA, *Chem. Ber.*, 1906, 39, 1538.
6. I. M. SIDAHMED and C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 2034.
7. A. D'APRANO and R. M. FUOSS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 400.
8. A. I. VOGEL "A Text-Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1971.
9. R. G. PEARSON, C. R. BOSTON and F. BASOLO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 804.
10. K. J. LAIDLER and P. A. LANDSKROENER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 200.
11. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1977, 1851.
12. K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", 2nd. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1965, Chap. 5.
13. W. E. JONES, L. R. CARRY and J. W. SWADDLE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1972, 50, 2739; G. A. LAWRENCE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 45, 1275; G. A. LAWRENCE and S. SIVACHITTANONT, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1980, 33, 277; D. A. PALMER and H. KELM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 3139; *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1981, 36, 89; G. DAFNER, D. A. PALMER and H. KELM, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, 61, 57.
14. W. G. JACKSON and A. M. SARGESON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, 17, 1348; W. G. JACKSON and C. M. BOGBIE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, 60, 115.

15. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. I*, 1981, 1515.
16. K. DAS, A. K. DAS and K. K. KUNDU, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1981, 26, 471.
17. I. M. SIDAHMED and A. M. ISMAIL, *Transition Met. Chem*, 1987, 12, 29.
18. M. J. DEWAR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3357.
19. R. G. BATES in "Hydrogen-bonded Solvent Systems", eds. A. K. GOVINGTON and P. JONES, Taylor and Francis, London, 1968, p. 49.
20. R. YAMDAGI and P. KEBARLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 2940.
21. R. L. KAY and T. L. BROADWATER, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1971, 16, 667.